

IMPLICATIONS OF FEEDBACKING TECHNIQUES ON STUDENTS' OUTPUTS AND ITS EFFECT ON THEIR PERFORMANCE AND ATTITUDE IN WRITING

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine how English teachers' written feedback affects students' writing performance and attitudes. Utilizing a purely quantitative research design, the study gathered data through writing assessments and a standardized survey questionnaire. A total of 160 Grade 7 to Grade 10 students from Hinlayagan National High School participated in the research. Their writing performance was assessed using a pre assessment and post assessment, evaluated through the six traits of writing rubric: ideas and content, word choice, conventions, organization, voice, and sentence fluency. This rated from needs improvement to excellent. The feedback given by teachers was based on students' outputs, focusing on correcting errors and providing guided suggestions. To measure students' attitudes toward written feedback, the researcher used a validated questionnaire adapted from the study of Cinkara and Galaly (2018), titled "*EFL Students' and Teachers' Attitudes towards Written Feedback in Writing Classes: A Case of Iraqi High-Schools.*" The results revealed that students generally valued and appreciated the written feedback provided by their teachers, acknowledging its role in helping them improve their writing performance. However, statistical analysis showed no significant relationship between students' attitudes and their actual writing performance, indicating that while feedback may enhance skills, attitude alone does not predict writing outcomes. The findings highlight the importance of giving students clear and constructive written feedback tailored to their learning needs. The study recommends that school administrators support teachers by offering professional development programs and

learning action cell sessions that focus on a range of effective feedback strategies. Doing so will help educators implement more impactful approaches in their writing instruction, ultimately improving students' performance in English.

Keywords: *Feedback Strategies, Written Outputs, Writing Performance, Attitudes*

INTRODUCTION

Writing is one of the English language skills students need to develop because it is crucial for written academic communication. Students make various learning mistakes in vocabulary, grammar, spelling, and pronunciation (Salawazo et al; 2020). However, Wahyuni (2017), emphasizes the value of providing feedback to students while they are still in the writing process.

In the same vein, Hyland (2003) outlines the main difficulties in writing instruction and presents some developed teaching strategies. Giving feedback and responding to students' writing using various forms of written feedback are important instructional practices. Similarly, Ahea et al. (2016) emphasized that feedback plays a vital role in enhancing students' learning and improving teaching effectiveness in higher education.

Feedback happens when teachers offer suggestions, criticism, or information on students' performance in order to help them grow as individuals. It might be viewed as a way for the students to be evaluated and know what their flaws are. According to Hattie and Timperley (2007), feedback is defined as information on one's performance or knowledge that is given by an agent (such as a teacher, peer, book, parent, or personal experience). A peer or instructor can offer constructive criticism, can offer a different approach, and a book can give knowledge to explain concepts.

Moreno (2019) defined feedback from his perspective, "In the field of second language acquisition feedback refers to the information that learners receive and can use to revise inter-language or reinforce their hypothesis". Students can, therefore, use the feedback from their lecturers to edit and double-check the structure of their written work.

Based on Ellis' (2009) paradigm for written corrective feedback (WCF), a study was carried out in the Philippines by Baculi, et al. (2012) to determine the sort of written corrective feedback that Filipino (ESL) teachers use the most frequently. From the four high school levels, 41 students gathered. Each group of written compositions was categorized, and modifications were made in line with the particular kind of feedback. According to the research, Filipino English (ESL) teachers primarily use both direct and indirect textual corrective feedback when reviewing student writing.

In the researcher's current situation, however, English teachers appear to undervalue the importance of providing comments on students' written work since they must manage 40 or more outputs, a time crunch, and other ancillary activities. The researcher has also seen that students who seem to have little or no interest in the writing-

related feedback offered to them may have caused professors to lose interest in providing it.

Thus, in order to develop an enrichment program for English classes, the researcher set out to record English teachers' feedbacking tactics and analyze the impact of teachers' feedback on students' outputs in the new normal. The findings of this study can help English teachers enhance their feedback techniques to inspire and further develop junior high school students' writing abilities.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine feedback strategies of English teachers and to determine the effects of teachers' feedback on students' writing performance and attitudes in the new normal.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What feedback strategies do English teachers use in students' written outputs?
2. What is the level of students' writing performance before and after the conduct of feedback strategies?
3. What is the students' writing attitude after feedback?
4. Is there a significant difference between students' writing performance in the pre and post-tests?
5. Is there a significant relationship between students' writing performance and their attitude towards writing?
6. What enrichment program could be designed in order to improve the students' writing performance and their attitude towards writing?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design to examine the effects of teachers' written feedback on students' writing performance and their attitudes toward writing. A descriptive method was used to gather and analyze numerical data through two instruments: a writing performance assessment and a standardized survey questionnaire. The writing tasks served as both the pre assessment and post assessment, allowing the researcher to measure the changes in students' performance after receiving written feedback. In addition, students' attitudes were evaluated using a validated questionnaire adapted from Cinkara and Galaly (2018) in their study "EFL Students' and Teachers' Attitudes towards Written Feedback in Writing Classes: A Case of Iraqi High-Schools." This approach enabled the researcher to quantify both writing improvement and student perceptions, leading to a clearer understanding of how feedback influences learning outcomes.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Hinlayagan National High School, a public secondary school in the municipality identified for having a significant number of junior high school students with low English performance. Based on the school's records, 287 out of 665 students, or 43 percent, received grades ranging from 75 to 79 during the first quarter of the 2021 to 2022 school year. This high percentage of learners falling within the lower performance bracket made Hinlayagan National High School a suitable research locale for the student respondents. The school is also known for its active participation in academic competitions aligned with the English curriculum, reflecting its strong engagement with language learning.

For the teacher respondents, two schools were included: Hinlayagan National High School and Kinan-oan High School. The English teachers from these schools were selected based on specific criteria, including their ongoing pursuit of graduate or postgraduate studies and their expressed willingness to participate in the study. Their academic engagement and professional interest in language teaching provided valuable insights into the feedback strategies they used in assessing students' written outputs.

Research Respondents

The study involved two groups of participants. The first group consisted of eight junior high school English teachers from Kinan-oan High School and Hinlayagan National High School. They were selected based on specific criteria: they must be public secondary English teachers with at least two years of teaching experience, currently handling only English subjects in junior high school, and must have expressed willingness to participate in the study. Teachers who met only one or two of these qualifications were not included. In cases where a participant withdrew, the study proceeded as long as the minimum number of teacher-participants was maintained.

The second group comprised 160 junior high school students from Hinlayagan National High School. These students were selected through simple random sampling from a total pool of 287 students who had obtained an average English grade between 75 and 79 during the first quarter of the 2021–2022 school year. To ensure equal representation, 40 students were randomly selected from each grade level (Grades 7 to 10) by drawing names from separate bowls designated for each level. Students who were selected but declined to participate were excluded from the final sample.

Distribution of Respondents

Group	School	Grade Level	Number of Respondents
A. Teachers (n=8)	Hinlayagan National High School	–	4
	Kinan-oan High School	–	4
Total (Teachers)			8

B. Students(n=160)	Hinlayagan National High School	Grade 7	40
		Grade 8	40
		Grade 9	40
		Grade 10	40
Total (Students)			160

In selecting the participants, the researcher collaborated with the public school district supervisors to identify individuals who met the established inclusion criteria for the study. Careful attention was given to ethical considerations, particularly in protecting the anonymity and confidentiality of all participants. To safeguard their identities, each participant was assigned a screen name or code, and all sensitive information was securely handled, with only the researcher having exclusive access to the raw data.

During the recruitment process, participants were formally invited through a letter of request, which was accompanied by an Informed Consent Form and the Interview Guide. The informed consent clearly stated that participation was entirely voluntary, and participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence, provided that they communicated their decision directly to the researcher.

Research Instrument

The study utilized two main research instruments, both designed to gather quantitative data. The first instrument was a printed writing assessment used to evaluate students' writing performance through a pre assessment and a post assessment. These assessments were conducted within the school setting and were supervised by English teachers who also provided written feedback on the students' outputs. The assessments were based on the Six Traits Writing Method developed by Spandel and Stiggins (1980), which evaluates writing across six key areas: ideas, organization, voice, word choice, sentence fluency, and conventions. This rubric provided a consistent and objective scoring system that allowed for measurable comparisons of student performance before and after feedback was applied.

The second instrument was a standardized questionnaire adapted from the validated study by Cinkara and Galaly (2018), titled *"EFL Students' and Teachers' Attitudes towards Written Feedback in Writing Classes: A Case of Iraqi High-Schools."* This tool was used to assess students' attitudes toward the written feedback they received. The questionnaire was distributed after the completion of the writing tasks, and students were instructed to respond honestly based on their experiences. Their responses were then encoded and analyzed statistically to determine trends and levels of agreement regarding the impact of feedback on their writing motivation and engagement.

To ensure ethical standards were upheld, parental consent forms were distributed and collected for all student participants. The students were also informed of the voluntary nature of their participation and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. All data collected from the writing assessments and questionnaires were treated with strict confidentiality. Only the researcher had access to the raw data, and all results were used solely for academic and research purposes. This structured and objective approach ensured the reliability of the findings and aligned with the principles of a quantitative research design.

Research Procedure

To begin the data gathering process, the researcher secured formal approval by sending request letters to the Schools Division Superintendent, the District Supervisor of Trinidad II, and the Principal of Hinlayagan National High School. Once approval was granted, informed consent forms were distributed to the parents or guardians of the student participants, along with assent forms for the students themselves. These documents explained the voluntary nature of participation and assured all parties that data would be treated with strict confidentiality.

Following consent, the English teacher administered the pre assessment to 160 students from Grades 7 to 10. The task required students to write a narrative essay about their personal experiences with modular distance learning. After submission, the teacher evaluated the written outputs using the Six Traits Writing Rubric developed by Spandel and Stiggins (1980), which covered ideas, organization, voice, word choice, sentence fluency, and conventions. After receiving written feedback based on their performance, the students then completed a second writing task. This time the students were focusing on the challenges they experienced during the pandemic. The post assessment was scored using the same rubric to ensure consistency and to measure growth in writing performance.

To supplement the writing assessments, students were also asked to complete a standardized questionnaire adapted from the validated instrument developed by Cinkara and Galaly (2018). This questionnaire assessed their attitudes toward teachers' written feedback and its perceived impact on their learning. The responses were collected, encoded, and analyzed statistically. All data, including scores from the writing tasks and the questionnaire responses, were used solely for research purposes and did not affect students' academic grades. This structured and controlled process ensured the reliability and objectivity of the findings, in alignment with the principles of quantitative research.

Data Analysis

The study aimed to determine the effects of teacher written feedback on students' writing performance and attitudes, and to assess the effectiveness of feedback strategies in a measurable way. To achieve this, quantitative data were collected and analyzed using structured instruments. These included students' writing outputs from both pre

assessment and post assessment tasks, as well as their responses to a standardized questionnaire adapted from the validated tool developed by Cinkara and Galaly (2018).

The students' writing tasks were scored using the Six Traits Writing Rubric developed by Spandel and Stiggins (1980), which evaluates key elements such as ideas, organization, voice, word choice, sentence fluency, and conventions. These scores were recorded from both the initial and final writing assessments in order to measure changes in performance after the application of teacher written feedback. The results were encoded and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to determine the extent of improvement across each writing trait.

To complement the performance data, the students' attitudes toward teacher feedback were assessed through the adapted questionnaire. The collected responses were analyzed using statistical tools, including percentages, mean scores, and correlation tests. A t-test and paired t-test were applied to examine the significance of the differences between pre and post assessment scores. The data analysis provided a clear and objective understanding of how teacher feedback influenced student writing and how students perceived its impact. This quantitative approach allowed for an evidence-based evaluation of feedback strategies within the English classroom context.

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the results of the study. Using statistical tools, the researcher discusses the findings on the effects of teacher written feedback on students' writing performance and attitudes, as well as the effectiveness of feedback strategies among junior high school students in Hinlayagan National High School for the school year 2021 to 2022.

Table 1. Feedback Strategies that English Teacher Used on Students' Outputs

Feedback Strategies	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Written feedback	3.19	Agree
2. Oral feedback	2.68	Agree
3. Peer feedback	2.66	Agree

Table 1 presents the different feedback strategies used by English teachers on their students' written outputs. Based on the data, it is clear that most students received written feedback, showing that this method is widely used and appreciated. Many students showed interest in understanding and correcting their mistakes through the written comments provided by their teachers. While written feedback was the most

common, some students also experienced oral feedback and feedback from their classmates, which shows that teachers are making an effort to support learning in different ways. This variety reflects a supportive and thoughtful approach, helping students improve their writing with guidance that matches their needs.

These results support the findings of earlier studies. Black and William (1998) pointed out that effective feedback has a strong influence on student learning and can improve achievement by as much as 70 percent. Hattie and Timperley (2007) also emphasized that feedback is most effective when it is timely, clear, and useful. In this study, students showed a clear preference for written feedback, which matches the findings of Carless and Chan (2017), who discovered that students prefer written comments because they are more detailed, specific, and easy to revisit. Still, the importance of oral feedback should not be overlooked, as it allows for a more personal interaction between teacher and student. Peer feedback also came into play, encouraging students to learn from and support one another. These different methods highlight the value of giving students feedback in ways that work best for them.

The responses gathered after the writing tasks showed that students believed written feedback helped them improve their writing skills. Their scores also showed noticeable improvement. This supports the findings of Alamis (2010), who has emphasized how written feedback helps students develop stronger writing. It also connects with the learning framework introduced by Krathwohl (2002), which describes how learners progress from remembering information to creating new ideas. In this case, teacher feedback served as a helpful tool that guided students to reflect, revise, and grow as writers. Table 1 provides a clearer view of this improvement by showing how students from Grades 7 to 10 performed before and after receiving different types of feedback.

Table 2. Level of Students' Writing Performance Before and After the Conduct of Feedback Strategies

Writing Performance	Before		After	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Ideas & Content	1.19	Needs Improvement	1.83	Adequate
Word Choice	1.05	Needs Improvement	1.46	Adequate
Conventions	1.03	Needs Improvement	1.35	Adequate
Organization	1.05	Needs Improvement	1.39	Adequate
Voice	1.03	Needs Improvement	1.52	Adequate
Sentence Fluency	1.02	Needs Improvement	1.26	Needs Improvement

Overall	1.06	Needs Improvement	1.47	Adequate
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Table 2 displays the findings of the survey conducted among students in Grades 7 and 10 after completing the writing tasks. The survey gathered students' views on how teacher feedback influenced their writing. The responses suggest that students recognize the value of feedback and its role in helping them grow as writers. However, while they acknowledge that feedback supports their progress, many still rely heavily on their teachers and appear to underplay their own responsibility in applying the suggestions to improve their work.

Prior to implementing any feedback strategies, the English teacher assessed students' writing using a standardized scoring range. A score of 3.0 was considered Excellent, scores between 1.2 and 2.9 were labeled as Adequate, and scores from 0 to 1.19 were categorized as Needs Improvement. The mean results from the students' initial writing tasks revealed the following scores: constructing ideas at 1.19, word choice at 1.05, conventions such as correct spelling, indentation, capitalization, grammar, and punctuation at 1.03, organization at 1.05, voice at 1.03, and sentence fluency at 1.02. These results clearly show that most students were performing at the Needs Improvement level across all writing traits. This aligns with research by Graham and Perin (2007), which highlights that developing writing skills is a common challenge among students, especially in areas such as clarity, organization, and mechanics.

None of the students initially achieved an Adequate or Excellent score, which signaled the need for targeted and purposeful feedback. Studies like those of Hattie and Timperley (2007) emphasize that constructive feedback can be a powerful tool in helping students improve their academic performance. Strategies such as providing specific comments, involving students in peer evaluations, and allowing opportunities for revision and editing can greatly support their writing growth. After implementing these feedback strategies, the students' writing performance improved. The average score increased from 1.06 in the initial task to 1.47 in the final writing task. Most students advanced to the Adequate level in areas like content, word choice, conventions, organization, and voice, though sentence fluency remained an area that required more support. While no student reached the Excellent category, the gains reflected meaningful improvement. These findings are consistent with earlier research by Kahyalar and Yilmaz (2016), which also highlighted how written feedback contributes to the enhancement of student writing quality. Overall, the results show that feedback is not only a helpful guide but also a key factor in improving students' confidence and competence as writers.

Table 3. Students' Writing Attitudes After Feedback

Learners' Attitudes towards Written Feedback	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Students pay attention to the teacher's written comments/feedback.	3.14	Agree
2. Students care about the quality of their writing.	3.10	Agree
3. Students want to have better marks in writing.	3.26	Strongly Agree
4. Students want to avoid errors in writing composition.	3.09	Agree
5. Students understand the teacher's way in highlighting errors.	3.21	Agree
6. Teachers' written feedback affects students' writing performance.	2.96	Agree
7. Students neglect teachers' negative comments.	2.76	Agree
8. Students take them into consideration to improve their writing with teachers' negative comments.	2.96	Agree
9. Students feel discouraged with your teachers' negative comments.	2.74	Agree
10. Students appreciate the teachers' positive comments.	3.28	Strongly Agree
11. Students get motivated with the teachers' positive comments.	3.22	Agree
12. Students feel confident with teachers' positive comments.	3.21	Agree
13. Students take seriously with the teacher's comments receive on their work.	3.29	Strongly Agree
14. Students' writing improves after receiving the teachers' feedback each time.	3.25	Agree
15. The teachers' written feedback improves your ability to write.	3.28	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.12	Agree

The results shown in Table 3 suggest that feedback plays an important role in helping students develop a more positive attitude toward writing and improve their writing performance. The highest-rated statements include “Students take seriously the comments they receive on their work” (3.29), “Teachers’ written feedback improves students’ ability to write” (3.28), and “Students appreciate teachers’ positive comments” (3.28). These results show that students value written feedback, especially when it is specific and encouraging. It also highlights how much they rely on teacher input to help them grow and feel more confident in their writing.

Meanwhile, the lowest-rated statements were related to how students respond to negative feedback. “Students feel discouraged by teachers’ negative comments” received a mean score of 2.74, while “Students neglect teachers’ negative comments” followed closely at 2.76. These responses indicate that while students generally accept feedback, negative comments can affect their motivation. This shows the need for teachers to be mindful in giving feedback just like correcting mistakes with care and using language that helps students improve without discouraging them.

These findings support the ideas of Ni'mah et al. (2016), who emphasized that students’ attitudes and writing apprehension play important roles in shaping their writing performance. When learners feel confident and supported, they are more likely to engage actively and put greater effort into their writing tasks. Akaydin and Kurnaz (2015) also pointed out that several factors, such as education, home environment, and personal characteristics, shape students’ attitudes toward writing. Altogether, these results show how valuable written feedback can be, especially when paired with a supportive learning environment. The overall mean of 3.12 confirms that students generally agree on the importance of feedback in helping them become better writers.

Table 4. Significant Difference between Students’ Writing Performance in the Pretest and Posttest

	Writing Criteria	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p-value	Decision
Pair 1	Ideas and Content	1.1938	.44151	12.069	0.000	Reject Ho
	Ideas and Content After	1.8313	.72876			
Pair 2	Word Choice	1.0503	.29336	7.950	0.000	Reject Ho
	Word Choice After	1.4591	.70029			
Pair 3	Conventions	1.0250	.15662	6.632	0.000	Reject Ho
	Conventions After	1.3500	.64623			

Pair 4	Organization	1.0500	.21863	6.958	0.000	Reject Ho
	Organizations After	1.3938	.67383			
Pair 5	Voice	1.0313	.17454	8.695	0.000	Reject Ho
	Voice After	1.5188	.72660			
Pair 6	Sentence Fluency	1.0188	.13607	6.526	0.000	Reject Ho
	Sentence Fluency After	1.2625	.50765			

Table 4 presents the significant difference between students' writing performance before and after the implementation of written feedback strategies. The data show a clear improvement in all six elements of writing: ideas and content, word choice, conventions, organization, voice, and sentence fluency. The mean scores for each component increased from the initial writing task to the final written output, which served as the post assessment. The computed p-value for each writing trait is 0.000, indicating that the results are statistically significant. Because of this, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the pre assessment and post assessment must be rejected.

Among all the writing traits assessed, ideas and content showed the highest t-value, suggesting that students made the most noticeable improvement in generating and developing their ideas after receiving feedback. This result indicates that the feedback process helped students better understand how to communicate their thoughts more clearly and meaningfully in writing. Improvements were also observed in word choice and organization, suggesting that students became more deliberate in selecting appropriate vocabulary and structuring their work in a logical manner. Although sentence fluency showed the least growth in mean score, the change was still statistically significant, pointing to overall progress in students' writing performance.

These results support the findings of Graham and Perin (2007), who emphasized the importance of direct instruction and feedback in improving student writing. The positive changes observed in this study align with the idea that clear, guided support can help learners identify areas for improvement and actively work on them. Troia (2006) also highlighted how instructional practices focused on writing skills lead to greater proficiency, especially when paired with consistent feedback. The improvements in all six traits, especially in the content and organization of ideas, show that students were able to internalize and apply the corrections and suggestions made by their teachers.

Furthermore, the feedback provided in this study was focused, actionable, and designed to help students build confidence in their writing. Students were not simply told what was wrong but were guided toward understanding how to improve. This thoughtful

approach allowed them to revisit and revise their work, which is essential in developing stronger writing skills. The results suggest that when feedback is used not as punishment but as support, students become more engaged and motivated to grow.

In conclusion, the findings in Table 4 demonstrate that written feedback is an effective instructional strategy for improving student writing performance. The significant gains across all writing traits show that students were able to make meaningful progress when given structured and constructive feedback. This supports the idea that feedback is not just a response to student work but a crucial part of the learning process. By providing specific guidance and encouraging self-reflection, teachers can help students become more confident and competent writers. The outcome of this study contributes to the existing literature on effective writing instruction and highlights the lasting impact that well delivered feedback can have on student achievement.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Students' Writing Performance and Attitudes towards Writing

	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-value	Interpretation	p-value	Decision
Writing Performance	19.8250	1.32963	0.039	Negligible Correlation	0.621	Accept Ho
Attitudes	24.8813	1.52287				

Table 5 presents the analysis of the relationship between students' writing performance and their attitudes toward writing. The computed r-value is 0.039, which indicates a negligible correlation between the two variables. Additionally, the p-value of 0.621 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no statistically significant relationship between students' attitudes toward writing and their actual writing performance based on the results of this study.

The implication of this finding is that while students may express interest in writing or hold generally positive or negative attitudes, these feelings alone do not necessarily predict or influence their actual writing outcomes. In other words, a student who enjoys writing may not always perform well in written tasks, and a student with a less favorable attitude may still demonstrate competent writing skills. This aligns with the idea that many

other factors, such as instruction quality, feedback received, prior knowledge, and writing practice, play a more direct role in shaping writing performance.

This assertion is supported by Göçer et al. (2014), who explored the relationship between students' attitudes, anxiety, and achievement in learning Turkish as a foreign language. The study revealed that learners' attitudes significantly influence their language performance, suggesting that a positive attitude toward language learning such as writing can support students' ability to express themselves effectively, while negative attitudes or anxiety may hinder their success. Similarly, Güneş (2021) explained that effective writing instruction starts with systematic, sound-based teaching methods that activate cognitive processes essential for literacy development. This suggests that cognitive readiness, rather than emotional preference, plays a more critical role in writing success. Together, these perspectives highlight the complex nature of writing development, where attitude may play a supporting role but is not the sole factor determining performance.

Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

- 1. Feedback Strategies Used by English Teachers.** English teachers employed written feedback strategies in responding to students' written outputs. These included marking the erroneous parts of the text and providing the correct form or structure. The feedback was direct and focused on guiding students toward improved clarity, accuracy, and coherence in their writing.
- 2. Students' Writing Performance Before and After Feedback.** During the pre-assessment, the writing performance of student participants was generally rated as needing improvement. This was especially evident in the areas of idea development, word choice, conventions, organization, voice, and sentence fluency. However, after the application of written feedback strategies and the completion of the post assessment, students demonstrated notable improvements across all writing traits.
- 3. Students' Attitudes Toward Written Feedback.** The majority of student participants expressed appreciation for the written comments provided by their teachers. They reported taking the feedback seriously and believed that it helped them improve their writing ability and achieve better marks. These responses indicate that students view teacher feedback as an essential part of their learning process.
- 4. Significant Difference in Writing Performance.** There was a statistically significant difference in students' writing performance between the pre assessment and post assessment. This suggests that the application of written feedback strategies had a positive impact on improving students' writing skills.

- 5. Relationship Between Writing Performance and Attitude.** The results indicated no statistically significant relationship between students' writing performance and their attitudes toward writing. This implies that while feedback contributed to performance improvement, students' attitudes alone did not directly influence their writing outcomes.

Conclusions

The implementation of feedback strategies significantly improved students' performance in writing as well as their attitudes toward the writing process. The findings of the study affirm the value of teacher feedback, especially written comments, in helping junior high school students enhance their skills in areas such as developing ideas, organizing content, choosing appropriate words, and improving sentence structure. When students received clear and constructive feedback, they were able to revise their work more effectively and produce better written outputs. This not only supported their academic growth but also strengthened their confidence as writers.

In addition, the use of feedback encouraged students to develop a more positive attitude toward writing. Receiving thoughtful comments and corrections motivated them to put greater effort into their work, not just to complete the task, but to understand and apply what they had learned. The study highlights the essential role of teachers in guiding students through meaningful feedback that promotes both improvement and engagement. With continued support, students are more likely to view writing as an opportunity for learning and self-expression, rather than as a task to be feared or avoided.

Recommendations

Considering the salient findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended by the researchers.

- 1. Integrating Feedback Strategies in Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions:** Teachers should be encouraged to explore and compare different types of feedback through regular group discussions in Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. These discussions should include comparisons between written feedback, oral feedback, and feedback delivered through digital platforms to provide a broader understanding of their effectiveness. Teachers may be guided to reflect on how each feedback type influences student engagement, motivation, and writing improvement. Sample outputs, case studies, and student responses could be analyzed collaboratively. Facilitators should also introduce research-based insights during LAC sessions to help teachers align their feedback strategies with current best practices in writing instruction.
- 2. Professional Development and Resource Support for Writing Instruction:** School administrators should provide continuous professional development opportunities focused on effective feedback strategies for writing. These may include training on how to give constructive written comments, use assessment

rubrics like the Six Traits Writing Model, and implement feedback cycles that encourage student revision. In addition to training, administrators should allocate resources for writing materials, student workbooks, and visual writing aids. Collaboration among teachers should be promoted through professional learning communities that focus on writing development. Moreover, schools should cultivate a culture that values writing not only as an academic skill but also as a tool for communication and expression across all learning areas. Integrating writing activities across subjects will help reinforce writing skills and promote interdisciplinary learning.

- 3. Development and Implementation of an Enrichment Program:** A structured enrichment program is recommended to further enhance students' writing performance and attitudes toward writing. This program should include activities such as guided writing workshops, peer editing sessions, and writing contests that encourage creativity and engagement. Teachers should use differentiated instruction techniques to meet the varied writing levels of students and provide opportunities for learners to reflect on the feedback they receive. The program can also incorporate progress monitoring tools such as writing portfolios or journals to track individual development. By fostering a more interactive and student-centered approach to writing, the enrichment program can sustain improvement and build students' confidence and interest in written communication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The protocol before the study's conduct was observed correctly. The researcher underwent the Research Ethics Committee review procedures and secured the "Clearance to Gather Data" before conducting the interviews to ensure that the process was normally following correct procedures or protocols.

The researcher secured proper permission and consent from the school administrators through an informed consent form, where they affixed their signatures that signified their willingness to participate voluntarily as the respondents of the study. The researcher ensured that the basic principles of research were followed throughout the study. These principles are anonymity and confidentiality, among others. They were informed of their rights as well as the objectives of the study, and they may withdraw their participation anytime they want. They were also assured of the proper data management and utmost confidentiality of the data gathered.

Further, it underwent an integrity test and citation audit to ensure that other researchers did not plagiarize the paper.

Proposed Enrichment Program in Improving the Students' Writing Performance and Their Attitude Towards Writing

Rationale

Writing is an essential skill that students need to develop in order to succeed in their academic and professional lives. However, many students struggle with writing, whether it is due to a lack of confidence, motivation, or skill. As such, it is crucial for teachers and school administrators to design and implement enrichment programs that can help students improve their writing performance and foster a positive attitude towards writing.

This proposed set of enrichment program components includes Writing Workshops, Peer Review Groups, Writing Contests, Journaling, Writing Prompts, Digital Writing Tools, and Guest Speaker Series. These programs aim to provide students with opportunities to practice their writing skills, receive feedback and support from their peers and mentors, and explore different writing styles and genres.

Writing Workshops and Peer Review Groups offer structured opportunities for students to receive feedback on their writing and learn from their peers. Writing Contests provide a competitive environment that encourages students to write creatively and explore new writing styles. Journaling and Writing Prompts provide opportunities for students to practice writing regularly and develop their creativity. Digital Writing Tools offer students a range of resources to explore and experiment with new writing techniques and Guest Speaker Series provide exposure to professional writers and their experiences.

The writing programs aim to improve students' writing skills and encourage a positive attitude towards writing. By providing a range of opportunities for students to explore, practice, and develop their writing skills, we hope to help them become confident and effective writers who are well-prepared for academic and professional success.

Program Objectives

The proposed enrichment program aims the following objectives:

1. to improve teachers' knowledge and skills in teaching writing effectively.
2. to enhance teachers' ability to provide constructive feedback and support to the students writing.
3. to facilitate the development of a positive and engaging learning environment that promotes writing.
4. to enhance students' writing skills through various enrichment programs.
5. to develop students' positive attitude towards writing and an appreciation for its importance.

6. to foster students' creativity, critical thinking, and communication skills through writing activities.
7. to gain students' exposure to various writing genres, styles, and techniques; and
8. to receive feedback and support that will help the students improve their writing abilities.

Mechanics

1. The School Head will be consulted and asked for technical advice on the suitability of the program.
2. The proposal will be submitted to the English subject coordinator for approval and inclusion in the Learning Action Cell Session before it is presented to the teachers in the department.
3. The program will be subject to discussion and open for suggestions by the teachers upon its presentation.
4. The program will be adjusted based on the recommendations of the teachers to meet the language learning requirements of the students.

Matrix

Writing Program Components	Description	Mechanics	Time Frame	Success Indicators
1. Writing Workshops	Conducting writing workshops on a regular basis where students can learn different writing techniques and styles and receive feedback on their writing. This can help students improve their writing skills and build confidence in their abilities.	Determine the focus or theme of the workshop (e.g. descriptive writing, persuasive writing, etc.). Invite a writing expert or teacher to facilitate the workshop or lead it yourself. Plan and prepare the materials and activities to be used in the workshop. Set a schedule and venue for the workshop. Invite students who are interested in improving their writing skills to join the workshop.	Writing workshops can be conducted over several sessions, with each session lasting around 1-2 hours. The number of sessions can range from 4 to 8, depending on the scope of the workshop and the availability of the participants.	Students written outputs and sample compositions from the workshops and the monitoring record of the students' level of performance.

<p>2. Peer Review Groups</p>	<p>Forming peer review groups where students can review and provide feedback on each other's writing. This can help students learn from each other and improve their writing skills through constructive feedback.</p>	<p>Divide students into small groups of 3-4. Assign a writing task or topic for each group to work on. Give clear instructions and guidelines for the peer review process. Allow time for students to read and evaluate each other's writing. Encourage constructive feedback and suggestions for improvement. Provide a checklist or rubric to guide students in their evaluation. Set a deadline for the completion of the peer review and the final draft.</p>	<p>Peer review groups can be conducted on a regular basis, such as once a week or twice a month. Each session can last for around 1-2 hours, depending on the length and complexity of the written pieces being reviewed.</p>	
<p>3. Writing Contests</p>	<p>Organizing writing contests with different themes or prompts to encourage students to write creatively and express their thoughts and ideas. This can also help in building their confidence in writing and provide motivation.</p>	<p>Decide on the criteria and guidelines for the writing contest (e.g. theme, length, genre, etc.). Determine the prizes or rewards for the winners. Promote the contest to the students and encourage participation. Set a deadline for the submission of entries. Select a panel of judges to evaluate the entries and choose the winners. Announce and award the winners in</p>	<p>Writing contests can be announced and opened for submissions for a period of 2-3 months. The winners can be announced and awarded prizes in a separate event, which can be held a few weeks after the submission deadline.</p>	<p>Students written outputs and sample compositions from the workshops and the monitoring record of the students' level of performance</p>

		a special ceremony or assembly.		
4. Journaling	Encouraging students to maintain a journal where they can write about their thoughts, experiences, and reflections. This can help them develop a habit of writing and improve their writing skills over time.	Provide each student with a journal or notebook for writing. Assign a specific time and place for journaling (e.g. 10 minutes at the start or end of each class). Encourage students to write freely and expressively. Provide writing prompts or topics for those who need inspiration. Respect students' privacy and allow them to choose what to share or keep confidential.	Journaling can be done on a daily basis, with each entry taking around 10-15 minutes. The program can be conducted over a period of 1-3 months, with the participants encouraged to continue journaling even after the program has ended.	Students written outputs and sample compositions from the workshops and the monitoring record of the students' level of performance
5. Writing Prompts	Providing students with writing prompts or topics that they can write about, which can help them develop their writing skills and creativity.	Provide a list of writing prompts or topics for students to choose from. Give clear instructions on how to use the prompts (e.g. write for 10 minutes, use the prompt as the first sentence, etc.). Encourage creativity and originality in their responses. Allow students to share their writing with the class or in small groups.	Writing prompts can be provided on a regular basis, such as once a week or twice a month. Each prompt can be given a deadline of 1-2 weeks, depending on the length and complexity of the written piece.	Students written outputs and sample compositions from the workshops and the monitoring record of the students' level of performance
6. Digital Writing Tools	Introducing digital writing tools such as online writing platforms, writing apps, and digital	Introduce and familiarize students with various digital writing tools (e.g. Google Docs,	Digital writing tools can be introduced and taught in a single session,	

	<p>writing tools that can help students improve their writing skills, including grammar, syntax, and vocabulary.</p>	<p>Grammarly, Hemingway, etc.). Give a demonstration on how to use each tool effectively. Assign a writing task or project that requires the use of digital writing tools. Allow time for students to practice and explore the tools. Encourage students to collaborate and share their work using the tools.</p>	<p>which can last for around 2-3 hours. The participants can then be encouraged to use the tools in their writing projects for the rest of the semester or school year.</p>	
<p>7. Guest Speaker Series</p>	<p>Inviting guest speakers, such as published authors or journalists, to speak to students about their writing experiences and techniques. This can inspire students and provide them with valuable insights into the writing process.</p>	<p>Invite guest speakers who are writers, editors, or experts in a specific field of writing (e.g. journalism, creative writing, etc.). Schedule a time and venue for the guest speaker to talk to the students. Provide background information about the speaker and the topic of the talk. Encourage students to prepare questions and engage in a Q&A session. Allow time for students to reflect and share their insights after the talk.</p>	<p>Guest speaker series can be conducted over a period of 3-6 months, with each session featuring a different guest speaker who can talk about their writing experiences and share their expertise. Each session can last for around 1-2 hours, depending on the availability and schedule of the guest speaker.</p>	<p>Students written outputs and sample compositions from the workshops and the monitoring record of the students' level of performance.</p>

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